

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

No7
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 698 sahifa,
1-iyul, 2025-yil.

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Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

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“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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NEW MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF ONTOGENESIS PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the effectiveness of modern educational technologies used in the teaching process of ontogenesis psychology and their impact on the quality of education. It explores how interactive and media-based methods enhance students' comprehension of psychological development across different life stages.

Key words: Ontogenesis, personality, psyche, modern technologies, cognition, psychology, interactive methods, cluster method, role-playing games, media-based educational technologies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ontogenez psixologiyasi fanini o'qitish jarayonida qo'llanilayotgan zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarining samaradorligi va ularning ta'lim sifati va o'quv jarayoniga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, interaktiv va media asosidagi metodlarning inson ruhiy rivojlanish bosqichlarini o'zlashtirishdagi o'rni yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ontogenez, shaxs, ruhiyat, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, tafakkur, psixologiya, interaktiv usullar, klaster usuli, rolli o'yinlar, media ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: В статье проанализирована эффективность современных образовательных технологий, применяемых в процессе преподавания психологии онтогенеза, а также их влияние на качество образования. Особое внимание уделено интерактивным и медийным методам, способствующим лучшему усвоению знаний о психологическом развитии личности на различных этапах жизни.

Ключевые слова: Онтогенез, личность, психика, современные технологии, мышление, психология, интерактивные методы, кластерный метод, ролевые игры, медиаобразовательные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

Ontogenetic psychology is a science that studies human development from birth to the end of life in an individual context. This discipline enables students to understand age-specific characteristics of the human psyche. Therefore, the application of modern pedagogical technologies is crucial for the effective teaching of this subject. The relevance of teaching ontogenetic psychology with modern technologies is supported by several important factors.

Firstly, it aligns with the demands of contemporary society. Today, the field of psychology is closely intertwined with digital information technologies. Various electronic programs, diagnostic tools, tests and platforms are actively used in psychological research, diagnostics, analysis and counseling. As a result, it is essential to equip students with up-to-date knowledge and skills in these areas.

Secondly, modern technologies provide an opportunity to study the processes of psychological development in a more visual and interactive manner. In ontogenetic psychology, the stages of mental development from birth to old age are interpreted through multiple theoretical frameworks. The use of technological tools makes these theories more accessible and understandable for students, thereby enhancing both engagement and retention.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Brief historical outline of the development of child psychology. Early theories of mental development. The importance of J.-J. Rousseau's ideas for the development of child psychology. The emergence of developmental (child) psychology in the mid-19th century. The idea of evolution in child psychology (C. Darwin, V. Preyer). The problem of mental development and its driving forces in foreign psychology. Biogenetic and socio-genetic direction in child psychology. Recapitulation theory as the first theoretical concept in child psychology. Concepts of human mental development by St. Hall, J. Baldwin. Normative approach to mental development by A. Gesell. The theory of three stages of child development by K. Buhler. Classical representatives of the theory of convergence of two factors – heredity and environment (V. Stern) and their modern followers (A. Anastasi). Psychological limitations of two-factor theories of child development.

The problem of age. Periodization of mental development. The socio-historical nature of the duration of childhood, the emergence and sequence of its individual periods. The problem of acceleration of mental development. The problem of periodization of mental development in childhood, adulthood and old age. A review of foreign theories of periodization (A. Gesell, S. Hall, K. Buhler, Sh. Buhler, E. Erikson, A. Wallon, J. Piaget, etc.). The problem of age periodization in domestic psychology. The concept of "age", the main criteria of age; understanding the significance of crises in the mental development of a child. Periodization of mental development based on the identification of the leading type of activity (A.N. Leontiev, D.B. Elkonin, M.I. Lisina). The current state of the problem of periodization in domestic and foreign psychology; development prospects. Sources, driving forces and conditions of a child's mental development. The importance of social conditions. Mental development and activity. Mental development and communication. Mental development and learning. Genotypic characteristics and maturation processes as prerequisites for mental development. Interaction of biological and social factors. Social inheritance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

These complex processes are illustrated with video materials, 3D models, graphics, and can be conveyed to students in a clear and understandable way using simulations. The widespread use of distance learning has made distance learning technologies relevant during the pandemic and beyond. Teaching the subject of ontogenesis psychology through online platforms (Zoom, Google Classroom, Moodle), interactive tests and video lessons allows for the continuous continuation of the learning process. Also, by encouraging students to be creative and independent thinkers, students work on independent projects, presentations and scientific research through technologies. This develops their ability to apply psychological knowledge in practice, analyze and creatively approach problems.

At the same time, the teacher's ability to effectively manage the lesson process is enhanced. New technologies allow the teacher to quickly transfer educational materials, monitor the level of knowledge of students, implement an individual approach and constantly update their lessons. The relevance of teaching the science of ontogenetic psychology based on modern technologies is determined by the need to convey the complex and theoretically rich content of this science to students in a convenient, understandable and effective way, to prepare them for practice and to train competitive, modern psychological specialists.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Importance of new pedagogical technologies.

Makes education interactive, interesting and effective. Develops the student's independent thinking, analysis and creative approach, helps to understand the changes in the human body in relation to life.

New pedagogical technologies that can be applied:

1. Interactive teaching technologies – "Brainstorming" allows for free expression of ideas about the different stages of a child's development. A successful question is to consolidate knowledge through questions and answers about the mental characteristics that arise at each age.
2. Case study – Analyzing problems in children's psychology through real or fictional events. For example: analyzing the emotions and behavior of a 5-year-old child and assessing them according to their developmental stage.
3. Cluster method – Visually constructing the stages of human development (infancy, childhood, adolescence and adulthood – Picture-1).

Picture-1: Application of the cluster method in the psychology of ontogenesis

4. Role-playing games – To practically demonstrate differences in consciousness, emotions and behavior by putting students in the roles of children of different ages.
5. Media educational technologies – Demonstrating the processes of human psychological development through video, audio and animation. For example: showing videos of Erikson's stages.

Students develop a correct understanding of the results and expected effects of age-related mental development. The educational process becomes interesting and effective. The ability to think scientifically and reflect is developed. The harmony of theory and practice is ensured.

Also, the results of using new modern technologies in teaching the subject of ontogenesis psychology are as follows: the interactivity of the educational process increases – students actively participate in the lesson process, which helps to master knowledge more deeply. Theoretical knowledge is combined with practice, visual materials and video lessons. The stages of mental development are more clearly understood through simulations. The level of student mastery increases. The materials are presented at a pace and in a form suitable for each student, improving learning outcomes.

Independent learning skills are developed – students are encouraged to study independently through online courses, tests and electronic textbooks. Modern knowledge and skills are formed, and IT skills important for the field of psychology are acquired (for example: statistical programs, digital tests).

Scientific research activities are activated – the possibilities for conducting scientific research expand through electronic databases and online psychological tests. Initiative and creative thinking are developed – students are given the opportunity to create independent posters and presentations. Education based on new technologies serves to deepen the understanding of the science of ontogenetic psychology, prepare for scientific and practical activities, and train competitive psychologists-specialists.

METHODS OF DEVELOPMENTAL PSYCHOLOGY

Features of observation and experimental methods in developmental psychology. Observation method, its varieties and requirements. Experiment in developmental psychology, its types. Features of the application of experimental methods in developmental psychology. Natural and laboratory experiments in child psychology. Ascertaining and formative research strategies. The main types of ascertaining experiments: "longitudinal" and "transverse" sections. The method of formative experiment as an alternative to the "section" method. Method of analysis of activity products. "Twin" method – its significance. Significance of cross-cultural research for solving problems of developmental psychology.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The use of modern technologies in teaching ontogenetic psychology not only improves the quality of teaching, but also develops the scientific and practical potential of students, their ability to conduct independent research and their skills in the effective use of information technologies. This is an important factor in the training of modern psychologists.

References:

1. E. G'. G'oziyev. Ontogenez psixologiyasi. O'quv qo'llanma. Noshir, 2010 y. – 360 b.
2. Jumayev N.Z. Ontogenez psixologiyasi [Matn]: o'quv qo'llanma / N.Z. Jumayev. – Buxoro: "Sadridin Salim Buxoriy" Durdoni, 2022. – 252 b.
3. O.V. Shapatina, E.A. Pavlova. Psixologiya razvitiya i vozrastnaya psixologiya / Samara: Izdatel'stvo "Univers Grupp", 2007. – 203 s.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №7

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.